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The Perceptions of Millennial English Teachers in the Use of Slangs by the Gen-Zs as a Lexis Phenomenon

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Abstract

The English language evolves due to various trends and technological advancements. As societies age, a new generation appears, and neologisms are bound to occur. This study highlights two generations: Generation Z (Gen Z) and the Millennials. This research aims to identify and compare that aimed to investigate the lexis phenomenon behind Gen-Z slang from the perceptions of five (5) Millennial English teachers who are or were employed as senior high school teachers within the grounds of the University of San Jose-Recoletos (USJ-R), and to discuss the issue of the generational communication gap. A phenomenological qualitative method, using one-on-one interviews and a questionnaire, was employed in four parts to gather data on knowledge and perceptions of Gen-Z slang use. Upon the analysis and the comparison of the various answers of the participants, results show that while Millennials view the evolution of the English language positively, the issue of the generational gap persists, depending on the knowledge of both the meaning and usage of Gen-Z slang by Gen-Zs during informal or casual conversations, both in class and on social media. Despite the challenges posed by the generational gap, this study indicates that Millennials can adapt to and appreciate the use of Gen-Z slang to bridge the gap between Millennials and Gen-Zs. This study validates the importance of highlighting the generational gap and how it threatens communication, especially when two generations collide and technological advancement advances. Furthermore, future studies can expand the number of participants and gather insights beyond Gen-Z and Millennials.

Keywords: *perceptions, millennials, English teachers, lexis phenomenon, generation z (Gen-Zs), slangs, qualitative, Cebu, USJ-R, senior high school, generational gap, social media*

Introduction

People require communication to exchange information in their daily lives. How we use words can affect how well our speech is received. Using trendy words often captures the audience's attention more effectively than generic speech; however, this depends on who your audience is and what they consider "trendy." This is similar to how Millennials often struggle to understand the slang of younger generations, such as Generation Z (Gen Z), born between 1997 and 2012, whereas Millennials are born between 1981 and 1996. As such, generational differences are prevalent due to technological advancement, which results in language and cultural changes.

Like previous generations, Gen Zs sometimes use their own slang in casual conversations. Slang is a vocabulary of informal words and phrases that convey meanings opposed to those of standard language. Linguists often explain slang as a lexical phenomenon in which language evolves to reflect changes in time, society, and culture. Slang can be playful, elliptical, or vivid vocabulary that is used among an unspecified number of people who belong to the same or similar group. This style of language is classified in sociolinguistics to identify group(s) that use particular words and phrases in informal language (Carrington, 2024). In every generation, slang words are created that reflect social, political, and cultural factors. Slang is also often used to express affection and closeness between members of the same group (Rahma & Moetia, 2024).

In every generation, slang words are created that reflect social, political, and cultural factors. Additionally, slang helps more easily identify people from a particular group or foster a sense of solidarity with members of the same group. Slang is also often used to express affection and closeness between members of the same group (Rahma & Moetia, 2024).

Gen Zs are undeniably the first digital natives, born into a world of technological advances and exposed to social media, smartphones, and the instant accessibility of information. This results in today's technology being highly regarded as a major contributor to shaping a generation's language and to the rapid development of how people communicate and interact, specifically in language evolution. Moreover, the primary means of communication in this generation is through social platforms (Jeresano & Carretero, 2022). Social media's influence on language is multifaceted, impacting vocabulary, syntax, pragmatics, and even phonetics. One of the most notable impacts of social media on language evolution is the proliferation of new vocabulary. Social media platforms are breeding grounds for neologisms, which are newly coined terms that often reflect contemporary culture and technology (Dembe, 2024).

There were numerous studies on Gen-Z slang and how generations influence language change and adaptation; however, the lack of studies on the role of the generational gap in miscommunication is what this study aims to investigate. The subject of those studies is Gen-Z slang in particular; this study focuses more on defining the role of the generational communication gap. This study assumes that both Millennials and Gen Z experience significant miscommunication due to the use of Gen Z slang in casual conversations within academic environments.

Research Questions

This study aimed to define the communication gap between the two generations by examining Millennials' perceptions and the impact of Gen-Z slang during casual interactions at the University of San Jose-Recoletos, Cebu City. This study sought to answer the following:

1. What are the common Gen-Z slangs that Millennial English Teachers know?
2. What are the experiences of millennial teachers trying to understand Gen-Z slang?
3. How do you, as a millennial teacher, perceive the impacts of using Gen-Z slang, specifically in conversations?
4. How do you feel towards the evolution of the language, considering the existence of Gen-Z slang?

Literature Review

The new generation breed has changed dialect evolution over time due to media exposure. Age is another important factor to consider because of how the generations affect one another (Sydnor, 2023). A similar study by Moremen et al. found that the older generation, including Baby Boomers and working adults such as Millennials, has lower confidence in their ability to understand texts from online sources, especially in data collection. Meanwhile, the younger generation, Generation Z, has greater knowledge of data collection and privacy due to their extensive use of social media. Moreover, no analytical technique can capture the separative effects of generational differences, and there are no instances of a group within the same demographic sharing a characteristic (Rudolph et al., 2020). These details show how generational gaps can shape how people communicate.

According to Jebaselvi et al. (2023), social media has undoubtedly transformed the way we communicate with one another. It now plays a crucial role in every aspect of our lives, affecting not only how we interact but also how we view and uphold interpersonal connections. The way we connect, share our views and experiences, and navigate the complexity of the contemporary social landscape is affected by this change in interpersonal communication, which has both positive and negative effects. The power of social media to connect people beyond geographical borders is one of the most dramatic effects on interpersonal communication. Through websites like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, people can connect with friends, family, and acquaintances wherever they are. Consequently, the world is now more connected globally.

In this regard, according to Soriano (2023), technology plays an important role in society, serving as an instrument for disseminating information, sharing opinions, and connecting people regardless of race, age, gender, or social status. It also paved the way for influencers to influence other people through the evolution of language and the rise of slang on social media. The purpose of slang is not to divide people on social media but to distinguish different social identities on social media. Using specific slang makes a person feel they belong to a particular group. Slang also serves as a bridge between people, helping them connect (Krycha, 2024).

The advancement of technology has led us to today's way of communication and information sharing: the internet. The internet is a means of communication that, for the first time in human history, allows many people to communicate at their convenience and on a global scale (Zarna, 2024). Since the Internet is an open virtual world, the identities, occupations, and cultural backgrounds of Internet users are diverse. As a carrier of ideas, the Internet language is undoubtedly a mixed bag. The methods of expression are flexible and varied, with an abundance of vulgarity and misspelled words. Additionally, Internet slang often relies on context or shared knowledge, making it inaccessible to those unfamiliar with specific online communities or trends (Yang, 2024).

Social media's influence on language is multifaceted, impacting vocabulary, syntax, pragmatics, and even phonetics. One of the most notable impacts of social media on language evolution is the proliferation of new vocabulary. Social media platforms are breeding grounds for neologisms, which are newly coined terms that often reflect contemporary culture and technology (Dembe, 2024). The linguistic landscape between Millennials and Generation Z is shaped significantly by societal influences, including cultural, technological, and environmental factors. A study comparing the slang of Millennials and Gen-Z reveals that rapid technological changes and cultural shifts more influence Gen-Z's slang. This generation tends to use abbreviations and creative mispronunciations more frequently than Millennials, reflecting a dynamic adaptation to digital communication platforms like TikTok and Instagram. The flexibility of their slang allows it to be used in both formal and informal contexts, showcasing their innovative approach to language. (Juli et al., 2024).

Another crucial factor that shapes Gen-Z slang is peer interaction. Studies suggest that slang is often adopted within social circles as a means of establishing identity and belonging (Jayanti et al., 2024). By employing terms that are less familiar to older generations, they create an insider language that reinforces social bonds while simultaneously alienating others (Vacalares et al., 2023).

Gen-Z slang is derived from neologisms, which are words or phrases that are newer than they used to be or that never existed before, due to a change in society, culture, or technology. Nowadays, the development of the internet and social media platforms has enhanced language creativity; as a result, new words have emerged in the language (Ibrahim, 2024). The process by which neologisms arise is called morphological processes; these involve the formation of new words. Understanding the sequence of morphological processes makes it evident why language itself evolves. The emergence of Gen-Z slang proves such a phenomenon exists and will always be in constant motion.

Another study examined the percentage of understanding of Gen-Z slang between Gen Z and Millennials. In word formation,

Millennials recognized commonly used slang like "matsalam," "marites," "dasurv," and "selfie." Gen-Zers were more familiar with newer terms like "ludz," "sorna," and "forda." Overall, Millennials identified 457 internet slang words, whereas Gen-Zers recognized 572, indicating greater proficiency among the latter. The same study explored word borrowing in internet slang, in which words from one language are integrated into another to improve comprehension. Examples include "sana all" and "salamuch" in English, as well as medical jargon such as "kanser" (used to express negativity) and "cyst" (a term of endearment like "sis"). The study's analysis reveals a notable difference in linguistic intelligibility between Gen Z and Millennials. Gen-Z participants scored an average of 11.48, indicating a high familiarity with emerging language expressions, while Millennials scored 6.74, reflecting only an average level of understanding. This gap highlights Gen-Z's greater linguistic adaptability and awareness of evolving internet slang, whereas Millennials show comparatively lower familiarity with these trends (Vacalares et al., 2023).

The existence of slang among Gen Zs has become widely known for its profound influence on the evolution of language. As a result, miscommunication has developed between Gen Z and Millennials, whether in the classroom or online. According to Sydnor's (2023) study, one factor to consider is the generational gap. Because of the gap in ages that correlates to the different values and behaviors of both generations, it became hard for them to understand and adjust to one another. Considering the values and behaviors learned by these generations in different ways, a study by Moremen et al. (2024) found that another factor affecting Millennials' use of slang is their lack of or low confidence in understanding online texts.

In the study by Jebaselvi et al. (2023), social media plays a vital role in shaping people's viewpoints and experiences, ultimately affecting how they communicate with one another. This proves how powerful social media is. On the same note, the study by Soriano (2023) states that, despite its advantages and disadvantages, social media has become a globally recognized platform for people to share insights, exchange information, and foster human interaction.

According to the study by Juli et al. (2024), with the use of technology, Gen Zs have developed another method to relay their thoughts directly: using abbreviations that can lead to mispronunciations. However, surprisingly, they were able to understand it in a short span of time, even before it became a trend. Although this method is not formally accepted, some Millennials have learned to adapt to it. In this regard, as noted by Dembe (2024), newly coined words first discovered on social media are spreading rapidly, affecting other generations. They may be confused about how and where these words came from.

Technology is also used by Gen Zs to create their own community and later develop their own communication style, which becomes their distinguishing feature from other generations (Vacalares, 2023). In addition, the study by Ayu Dwi Jayanti (2024) found that Gen-Zs used slang due to frequent peer interaction to establish their social identity and create a sense of belonging. On the other hand, Millennials had difficulty using social media because Gen-Z slang invaded it, causing unfamiliarity among other generations, specifically Millennials. Furthermore, the aforementioned studies have provided a strong foundation for this study regarding the factors that might influence the emergence of Gen-Z slang.

Methodology

Research Design

A phenomenological qualitative method was used in this study through a one-on-one interview, focusing on the impact of Gen-Z slang and on how Millennials define it. Afterwards, the researchers conducted interviews to gather each millennial's perceptions and attitudes towards Gen-Z slang. This qualitative study has employed discourse analysis and phenomenological research designs to investigate perceptions of Gen-Z slang among English Millennial teachers who are or were employed at the University of San Jose-Recoletos (USJ-R).

This phenomenological research explains that everyday experiences can influence our knowledge and understanding of a particular situation. According to phenomenologists, knowledge and understanding are embedded in our everyday world, and they believe that knowledge cannot be quantified or reduced to numbers or statistics. Furthermore, phenomenologists believe that truth and understanding of life can emerge from people's life experiences (Byrne, 2001).

Participants

This study consisted of five (5) Millennial English teachers employed in the senior high school department of the USJ-R, male or female, and in good health. To ensure the data gathered was consistent with the objectives of this study, purposive sampling was used to select participants who met the study's eligibility criteria.

Given that only five (5) teachers represent the Millennial generation due to the limited number of employed teachers and their time available for the interview. The findings of this research are limited and may not be generalized to represent the Millennials as a whole. However, considering that these Senior High School Teachers have been teaching English and Communication-Related Subjects for more than a year already, they are found to be viable and reliable enough to comprehensively and extensively elucidate the changes and phenomena they have observed among their students over time. Guided by their linguistic competence in analysis and in recognizing the disparity, the minimal number does not differ from larger ones in terms of the reliability of the data gathered from them.

Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire via Google Forms was created, and semi-structured interview guides were used, which are predetermined sets of topics and themes that allow for flexibility and follow-up questions to understand the complex social and cultural context and provide the needed data. The three experts in the field review this set of questionnaires. The researchers then used a framework matrix to organize and analyze the collected data, which were arranged in cases and columns. Its primary purpose was to balance and reduce the number of data while retaining the original interviewees' responses.

Procedure

Before the study began, the researchers coordinated with the Senior High School department to facilitate profile interviews and arrange convenient times for participants, avoiding disruptions to their teaching schedules. As the schedules were finalized, each participant was provided with a consent form explaining the study's objectives, confidentiality measures, and their right to withdraw at any time. The researchers further informed them that the interview was audio-recorded with the participants' permission.

Data Analysis

Data were gathered through one-on-one semi-structured interviews with participants coordinated through the Senior High School department to avoid disrupting teaching schedules. Consent forms were provided, ensuring confidentiality, voluntary participation, and permission for audio recording. The digital interview guide covered four key themes: familiarity with Gen-Z slang, communication strategies, language evolution, and the impact of slang on classroom conversations. Each session lasted up to an hour and was transcribed for thematic analysis. Codes were assigned to relevant data, organized into patterns, and developed into themes to capture participants' perceptions and experiences.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher upheld the study's integrity to protect participants, society, and the environment. The research was conducted responsibly and transparently, ensuring respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. Participants were treated as autonomous individuals, with special care given to those with diminished autonomy. Risks were minimized, benefits maximized, and fairness maintained throughout the process. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Recoletos Ethics Review Office, and participants provided informed consent to participate voluntarily. The study also complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to safeguard participant information.

Each participant received an in-person invitation and an emailed Informed Consent Form explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and confidentiality measures. Recruitment letters were sent to the chairperson, dean, and principal for transparency. Participation was voluntary, with no incentives other than a message of appreciation. All interviews were conducted in a respectful and culturally sensitive manner to avoid discomfort, especially since some slang terms discussed could be perceived negatively. Participants, considered non-vulnerable adults, provided informed consent and were reminded of their right to withdraw or request data deletion at any time.

All collected data, including consent forms and interview recordings, were securely stored on password-protected, encrypted devices and scheduled for deletion after three years. Transcriptions were anonymized, and access was restricted to the research team. After each interview, participants were debriefed and provided with referrals if needed. The study posed minimal risk, with researchers ensuring a safe and supportive environment. The findings provided insights into Millennial teachers' perceptions of Gen-Z slang, contributing to understanding intergenerational communication.

Results and Discussion

The Common Gen-Z Slangs that Millennial English Teachers Know

Table 1. *A list of 40 slang words*

sanaol	nays	forda	LMFAO
manser	perpek	tenkyu	TBH
lezzgo	korek, koriq	labyu	AFAM
g	ghurl	awit	FR
fav, fave	matsalam	sorna	F2F
y'all	lodi	galawan	RN
ge	erp	cutie	ATM
ppl	dai	lablab	BTW
labs	shat	kyut-kyut	DM
tnx	beshie	HBD	PM

Table 1 below lists 40 slang words the researchers provided to participants during Part 1 of the interview to gauge their understanding of Gen Z slang. The five (5) teachers were asked to answer one of three choices: 1) "I know of the slang and its meaning," 2) "I know of this slang but not its meaning," or 3) "I do not know this slang."

On the other hand, the overall results of Part 1 from the interview are gathered through a matrix table. Table 2 showcases what

Millennial English Teachers generally know about a majority of Gen Z Slang and their meanings. Results also showed an outlier, Participant 5 (P5), who knew Gen Z slang but not most of the meanings. This is important to consider because not all teachers will interact with their students the same way, and thus may or may not gain the proper context of certain slang.

Table 2. *Researchers' Assessment of Teachers' Knowledge of Gen-Z Slangs*

Participants (P)	Choice 1	Choice 2	Choice 3
P1	39	1	0
P2	36	2	0
P3	31	8	1
P4	36	1	3
P5	3	37	0

The following tables showcase themes and subthemes that have been observed from the answers provided by the participants. These themes provide a general insight into the thoughts of the teachers.

Table 3. *Challenges in Learning and Adapting to the Trend of Using Gen-Z Slangs*

	Significant Statements	General Description of the Sub-theme
Different insights of the Teachers regarding the slang words produced by Gen-Z	<p>P1: Sometimes the use of slangs in classroom environment is informal especially if it's during discussions. Sometimes some adults find it hard because they can't understand. Sometimes I was amazed hearing it from them.</p> <p>P2: It can always make the conversation alive, but not for all occasions.</p> <p>P3: It's good for casual conversations but sometimes, gen z students bring it to class and it is distracting.</p> <p>P3: It is highly overused. It can cause more confusion. In professional settings like the classroom, it is highly discouraged to use these slangs. They are called slangs in the first place.</p> <p>P4: Nothing special. I understood their conversation most of the time. Other acronyms seem difficult to understand. I have adapted "yupak". I also enjoyed some elab words. To be honest, I have no problem using it while outside of the classroom. It's interesting although it causes confusion sometimes. It should be addressed accordingly based on the nature of communication.</p> <p>P5: They are disrespectful and confusing.</p>	<p>Overall, this theme discusses differing opinions of teachers about how Gen-Z's slang should be used at the appropriate time, wherein it should not create a conflict with the formality of conversations. It also gives emphasis on how the language evolves and its contribution to the teacher-student relationship.</p>
Communication Strategies of the teachers while interacting with their Gen-Z students	<p>P1: I easily adapt to the languages they use and try my best to learn so I can relate with the conversation. As a teacher, of course you should know your tone and when to use those slangs. If you think it's not applicable then don't use it. So it really depends on the situation.</p> <p>P2: It's just going with what's new. You have to make sure that it is appropriate and applicable to the given topic.</p> <p>P3: If I don't know the meaning of it, I ask them and for casual conversation I do use this slang sometimes to try to relate.</p> <p>P4: it should be done appropriately based on the level of formality of your post. I see to it that I won't be left behind.</p> <p>P5: I listen well to them</p>	<p>This theme encompasses how the teachers adapt to the evolving process of language, despite the existence of a generational gap between generations. They demonstrate an openness to exploring and learning a new way of conversing, aiming to integrate a holistic connection with their students. In addition, their responses also suggest fostering a healthier and safer environment for their students to express themselves.</p>

In Table 3, the first theme is divided into two sub-themes; the first sub-theme is about different insights among the teachers regarding the slang words produced by Gen-Zs. P4 mentioned in one of their statements that Gen-Z slang is interesting as it does not exist in the vocabulary among the Millennials, and that confuses them. In addition, P2 and the rest of the participants also mentioned that with the use of slang words, it would make the conversation lively, but not to the extent of overusing them, especially in a classroom setting. According to the study of Juli, N. A. et al (2024), Gen-Zs use slang because they want to capture the main highlight of their thought by being direct to the point while conversing with other people. They are not used to small talk like what other Millennials and older generations are doing. In the same study, it also indicates the different perceptions of Millennials and Gen Zs in utilizing slang words depending on their meaning.

In the context of the second sub-theme, which is the different communication strategies of the teachers while interacting with their Gen-Z students, where teachers are necessarily modifying how they interact with their students, given that the generational gap persists. As stated by P1 and P3, it is very crucial to know the proper tone in speaking slang words because some of them contain multiple meanings that could cause ambiguity, and in situations where they are not familiar with the new word, they would often ask or research to obtain the meaning.

According to the findings from the study of Zakariya (2025), educators must modify their teaching strategies into a student-centered approach because Gen Zs are more interactive compared to other generations. They are known for being vocal and open to sharing their opinions, thoughts, and ideas. This generation is into collaborative learning. As a tool to promote this teaching strategy, the teachers may integrate technology to develop the critical thinking skills of the students as well as their communication techniques. In that way, teachers can achieve an effective learning environment that is beneficial for both without compromising the freedom of the students to express themselves through language.

Considering the sample size of this study, the views or statements from the five (5) Millennial English teachers do not reflect the entirety of the Millennial generation, as there exist Millennials who are well-versed with Gen-Z slangs; though, their experience and profession highlight the daily encounters of Gen-Z slangs as English teachers, both the advantages and disadvantages. Their statement reveals that there is a need for understanding and cooperation between educators and students to bridge the gap in language and learning.

Although this study provided five (5) participants as the source of data, this research's data is limited due to the number of respondents, but it is sufficient to justify the multiple perceptions, given the profession and experience of the participants. As such, the data inquired is proven valuable in formulating the perceptions of Millennials and how Gen-Z slangs are perceived

Table 4. *Implications of Gen-Z slang toward the evolution of the English Language with the existence of Social Media*

	<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>General Description of the Sub-theme</i>
The Rapid Lexical Expansion in Social Media	<p>P1: The evolution of the English language today is both fascinating and fast-paced. Technology, social media, and global interaction have accelerated the creation of new words, meanings, and expressions. It's very dynamic.</p> <p>P2: They are the medium of transmission of language, and they always make it alive no matter what season we have.</p> <p>P3: It can be a platform to educate melinials and baby bloomers on the meaning of the slangs and when to properly use it.</p> <p>P4: Social media is an effective platform to showcase a person's creativity. We may create contents for information, entertainment, business, and persuasion purposes.</p>	<p>The theme refers to the role of social media on the lexical expansion of Gen-Z slang and how Millennials respond to such a role in determining the implications of the evolution of the English language.</p>
Insights on the Morphological Processes and Usage Behind Gen-Z Slangs	<p>P2: I actually don't know their [Gen Z acronyms like "LMFAO" or "FR"] meanings yet.</p> <p>P5: I don't use [acronyms] it in my conversations.</p> <p>P1: Sometimes it [clipping] helps especially if you're in a hurry.</p> <p>P3: [Clipping is] It's downright lazy.</p> <p>P4: It [Clipping] is interesting. Sometimes, it is annoying. Most of the time, it makes my head hurt.</p> <p>P2: [Compounded words] They are really representations of the times like whenever something has happened, expressions really do come up.</p> <p>P4: I am amazed by [compounded words] it. It indicates the creative minds of people. It enables us to be current and up to date.</p>	<p>This theme revolves around three morphological or word formation processes: acronyms, clipping, and compounding, which are prevalent in social media. Unlocking what knowledge or perception among Millennial English teachers can bring about indications of whether such Gen-Z slang is appropriate or not.</p>

Table 4 reveals the linkage between Gen-Z slang, social media, and the evolution of the English Language from the perception of Millennials. After all, for Gen-Zs, a study by Vacalares et al. (2023) states that Gen-Z individuals engage in 2-3 social media platforms. daily, namely YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok, their study proves that nowadays, Gen-Zs use multiple social media applications regularly, which instantly exposes them to internet slang or newly coined words.

In Table 4, there are two main themes in the findings and this is the rapid expansion of vocabulary on social media and the morphological processes behind every Gen-Z slang word. There is a strong belief in the generation of Millennials that the advancement of technology has created a fast-paced environment for language evolution. For them, technology has become a "gateway" for new words to be born and spread quickly in which aligns with some existing studies that emphasize the role of technology in enhancing the English Lexicon through neologisms and jargon (Huseynova, 2024).

The interaction in digital media allows real-time language changes, a complete contrast to the process of dissemination of new words with the help of literature and journalism. The study reveals three morphological processes that are commonly used to form Gen-Z slang. The first one is acronyms, which causes difficulty for Millennials in understanding Gen-Z acronyms like "LMFAO" or "FR". Some of the participants even admitted that they are not familiar with it. The second is Clipping, in which, as per the result, there were mixed reactions to clipping, where words are shortened to form a new word. Some of the Millennials focus on its convenience, while some say it is another way to tolerate laziness. Lastly, the compounding in which two or more words are combined to form a new word. Millennials find this method creative.

Furthermore, the five (5) Millennial English teachers recognize the role that technology plays in shaping the evolution of language and the Gen-Z slang rapid expansion. Millennials also show their appreciation for the creativity behind the compounded words, but find

the inconvenience and laziness in using acronyms and clipped words. The lack of understanding about how language evolves often hinders some Millennials from incorporating Gen-Z slang into how they communicate.

Table 5. *The evolution of communication is impacting different formalities during conversations*

	<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>General Description of the Sub-Theme</i>
The Frequency of Using Slang Words by Gen Z Affects Formalities in Language	<p>P2: It [Gen-Z slangs] sounds informal in a way that even [if] you are educated, you sound like [you're] not.</p> <p>P3: It does not use a long time to express your thoughts because the words are shortened. But it is ineffective to be used specially if you have a specific goal in communicating.</p> <p>P4: If you guys share the same knowledge, good. If not, this will be a ground for miscommunication. This may complicate (to) worse cases.</p> <p>P5: It creates confusion</p>	This theme addresses the tension between linguistic innovation and traditional standards, focusing on how Gen-Z's widespread use of slang is affecting and reshaping how formalities within conversation are perceived.
Gen-Z Slangs in Class Environments	<p>P1: They [Students] use [it] inappropriately without thinking [of] the environment or the people they are talking to.</p> <p>P2: I find it inappropriate for the students to use Soafer especially when we are in a writing class because there's a tendency that they are going to write it in an essay type of activity.</p>	This theme examines how the use of slang affects interactions between students and teachers, potentially creating gaps in understanding or shifting the tone of classroom discussions.
Impacts on Students	<p>P1: They [Students] will grow as an expressive communicators.</p> <p>P2: Always explain to them the importance of formality in all aspects. We always have to inform them when is the right time to use them or not.</p> <p>P3: It's okay as long as [Gen-Z slangs] used in casual but not in professional conversations.</p> <p>P4: I see them [students] prosper. It indicates how their minds function well through adapting to what is current. If they use it to their gain, they will surely be successful.</p> <p>P5: It creates a more interactive conversation</p>	This theme focuses on how Gen-Z slangs impact student communication and the formal learning of the English language to develop their communication skills.

Lastly, Table 5 shows that communication, especially among Gen Zs, is reshaping language use across different social settings, from formal to casual. With the rise of digital platforms and social media, Gen Z frequently includes slang in their everyday speech, influencing how formal or informal those conversations become. The first sub-theme highlights how slang words blur the line between casual and formal language, as stated by P2: It [Gen-Z slangs] sounds informal in a way that even [if] you are educated, you sound like [you're] not. This aligns with how slang sometimes leads to misunderstandings, as expressed by P3.

The use of Gen-Z slang can be ineffective, especially if you have a specific goal in communicating, and P4: If you guys share the same knowledge, good. If not, this will be a ground for miscommunication. This may complicate to worse cases which aligns with a similar study that investigated faculty within its chosen institution, the faculty reported that Gen Z slang "lowers the formalities in speaking and writing," is sometimes mistaken for typos and leads to confusion, especially abbreviations like "POV" or "ROFLOL," unless context is provided (Estrada, Gonzaga & Racial 5).

The second sub-theme examines the entry of slang into educational spaces, potentially affecting communication between students and teachers. P1 mentions that they [Students] use [it] inappropriately without thinking [of] the environment or the people they are talking to in reference to how Gen Z tends to forget that academic environments like a classroom require more appropriate and understandable words to properly communicate ideas within academic discussions. P2 also states I find it inappropriate for the students to use Soafer, especially when we are in a writing class, because there's a tendency that they are going to write it in an essay-type activity. This is a sentiment shared in a study by another teacher "They will get used to it... they tend to misspell the words... it should be corrected in formal context" That study observed that while the teachers may tolerate slang in informal writing, it must be actively discouraged in formal essays (Ignacio et al. 16). Thus, while in some cases, slang can foster relatability and peer connection, excessive use may lead to reduced clarity in academic expression, hinder the development of proper writing and speaking skills, and even impact how students are perceived in formal learning contexts.

The third sub-theme reveals how the frequent use of Gen-Z slang influences students' communication abilities and their development in learning formal English. As students are immersed in digital platforms and social media, slang becomes a natural part of their vocabulary. This can improve their ability to communicate with their peers in dynamic, relatable, and expressive ways, as P1 states: They [Students] will grow as expressive communicators showing that slang can and does foster creative expression and connection in casual interactions.

However, frequency may affect the students' development in formal language, which is a key part of academic, professional, and official communication. Teachers are expected to guide students on the use of appropriate language. P2 emphasizes this responsibility in their statement: Always explain to them the importance of formality in all aspects. We always have to inform them when it is the right time to use them or not.

Results show that using slang is not inherently problematic, as observed by P3: It's okay as long as [Gen-Z slangs] are used in casual but not in professional conversations. Clear recognition of that, while slang can foster relatability and engagement, students must understand that there is a boundary between casual and formal discussions. Another acknowledges that the use of slang is a sign of adaptability, P4: I see them [students] prosper. It indicates how their minds function well through adapting to what is current. If they use it to their gain, they will surely be successful, highlighting that when used thoughtfully, slang can exist with formal language learning and even contribute to students' communication success.

Conclusions

The Gen-Z Slang has become another way to communicate, not just for this generation but also for the other generation who often has direct contact with them, specifically the Millennials. It is very evident how impactful slang is, as Millennials strive to understand and adapt to it, whether in casual conversation or in classroom-type settings. The study has become an instrument for these generations to understand the evolution of language and experience its advantages and disadvantages.

Based on the data gathered, the use of slang has become a trend, leading to the rise of newly coined words in the dictionary. With this aid, it has shaped different perceptions among Millennial English Teachers. Their views indicate that, despite the downsides and sometimes the lack of formality of using slang in a classroom setting, it can help students express themselves in their own words. On a related note, the presence of slang words undeniably became beneficial. Statements from the Millennial English Teachers imply that, because they were able to learn a new variant of language, they found slang words interesting to learn and explore.

In contrast to how they verbally adapt to it, some participants refused to fully conform to its existence due to unfamiliarity and, reputedly, a lack of respect. These participants are still encountering significant challenges in acquiring Gen-Z slang because of its complexity and how the two generations differ from each other. To integrate themselves into the trend of language, they had to create their own alternatives by looking up the meanings of specific slang terms or simply asking Generation Z (Gen-Zs) for help.

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